

5,7,4'-Trimethoxy-4-phenylcoumarin from Roots of *Indigofera oblongifolia*

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5,7,4'-Trimethoxy-4-phenylcoumarin has been isolated from the roots of *Indigofera oblongifolia* and characterised by spectroscopic methods.

Indigofera (Linn.) is a large genus (Fam : Leguminosae) and found abundantly in West Rajasthan. The plant *I. oblongifolia* is known for its therapeutic value, and various parts of the plant are reported in indigenous systems of medicine¹. In continuation of our previous work², here we report the isolation of 5,7,4'-trimethoxy-4-phenylcoumarin from roots of the plant along with β -sitosterol and β -sitosterol- β -D-glucoside.

The air-dried and powdered roots of *I. oblongifolia*, collected from village Utwan in West Rajasthan, were extracted with acetone. The resulting syrup was concentrated and on usual chromatography over silica gel afforded a compound which was crystallised from EtOH as needles, m.p. 150–52°. Elemental analysis and mass spectrum confirmed its molecular formula as C₁₈H₁₆O₅. Electronic³, ir⁴ and ¹H nmr⁵ spectra of the compound are characteristic of 4-phenylcoumarin indicating the compound to be 5,7,4'-trimethoxy-4-phenylcoumarin. This is the first occurrence of 5,7,4'-trimethoxy-4-phenylcoumarin in genus *I. oblongifolia* and the second from a natural source.

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